

**BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA XALQ OG'ZAKI
IJODINI O'RGATISH ORQALI MA'NAViy-AXLOQIY SIFATLARNI
SHAKLLANTIRISH**

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Buxoro shahar 38-maktab boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisi

Annotation. In this article discussed the proverb and its associated genre features, the proverbs in primary school textbooks, and the role of folk proverbs in the spiritual and moral education of elementary school pupils was carried out.

Key words. Proverbs, folklore, textbooks, international genres, spiritual education, moral qualities.

Maqol xalqning asrlar mobaynida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy hayotda to'plagan tajribalari, kuzatishlari asosida yuzaga kelgan ixcham chuqur mazmunga ega bo'lgan og'zaki ijod janrlaridan biridir. Maqol atamasi arabcha – qavlun- gapirmoq, aytmoq, bir xilda tushuniladigan ibora, ifodalar, asosan, maqol janrini tashkil etadi. Demak, maqol xalq ommasining muayyan voqea, hodisalar haqidagi xulosalari, hukmi va tavsiyalarini mujassamlashtirgan o'ziga xos badiiy shaklga ega bo'lgan ifoda va iboralardan iborat.

Maqol o'z tabiatiga ko'ra xalqaro janr hisoblanadi. Dunyoda o'z maqollariga ega bo'lmagan xalqning o'zi yo'q. Chunki har bir xalq hayotiy tajribalarini maqollar shaklida avlodlarga qoldiradi. Shuning uchun ham turli xalqlar og'zaki ijodida mazmun va shakl jihatidan bir-biriga yaqin hamda hamohang maqollar o'xshashliklar, umumiyliklar mavjud. Buyuk rus yozuvchisi L.N.Tolstoy "Har bir maqolda men shu maqolni yaratgan xalq siymosini ko'raman" deb yozganida to'la haqli edi.

Boshlang'ich sinflarda maqollarni o'rganish orqali o'quvchilar og'zaki nutqini o'stirish bilan bir qatorda ular orqali o'quvchilar ongiga turli insoniy fazilatlar singdiriladi. Bunda quyidagilarga e'tibor beriladi:

Maqollar tajribada sinalgan fikrni tasdiqlaydi. Masalan: “Hunarli kishi xor bo`lmas” (1-sinf), “Hunar bolsa qo`lingda, non topilar yo`lingda” (3-sinf), «Yolg`iz otning changi chiqmas, Changi chiqsa ham dong`i chiqmas”(4-sinf) maqollarida hunari orqasidan kishining yaxshi turmush kechirishi hamda kishilar orasidagi ahillikning ahamiyati ifodalangan;

Tabiatda sodir bo`lgan voqea va hodisalarni jamiyat hayotiga (ko`chma ma`noda) boshlaydi. Inson uchun uning zarurligi ochiladi. Masalan:

Bog`ni eksang bog` bo`ladi,

Botmon dahsar yog` bo`ladi.

Boqimsiz bog` tog` bo`ladi.

Yurak-bag`ring dog` bo`ladi;[3]

Maqol mazmunida narsalarning o`ziga xos xususiyati, mohiyati ochiladi va bu inson hayotiga ham bog`liq holda, ma`no jihatidan tarbiya mazmunini beradi. Masalan: «Do`stsiz boshim-tuzsiz oshim» (4-sinf), «Bulbul chamanni sevar, odam Vatanni» (1-sinf);

Maqollardagi muhokama va tafsilot inson, jamiyat va ayrim predmetlarning mohiyatini eslatish bilan birga, o`quvchilar fikrini uyg`unlashtiradi, tarbiyaviy ta`sir ko`rsatadi. Masalan: ”Ona yurtning- oltin beshiging” (4-sinf), ”Erinchoqlik boshga balo keltirar” (4-sinf).

Axloq, odob bahsidagi maqollarni tahlil etish orqali xalqning hukmi ifoda etiladiki, bu maqollarni o`rganish orqali o`quvchilar asrlar davomida avloddan-avlodga o`tib kelayotgan eng oliyjanob fazilatlar haqida fikrga ega bo`ladilar. Jumladan, “Ochko`zlik yomon odat, Keltirar u falokat” maqoli mazmuni 1-sinfda “Ochko`z sichqon” ertagi mazmuniga bog`lab o`rgatiladi. Bunda ochko`zlik insonni halokatga eltuvchi narsa ekanligi, nafsibalolik oxir-oqibat kulfat keltirishi tusuntiriladi. O`quvchilar bunday xislatga ega bo`lmasligi uqtiriladi. Ertak mazmunidan xulosa chaqartiriladi.

Ilm-fanni egallashga, hunar olishga yo`naltiruvchi maqollar o`quvchilarning bilim olishga bo`lgan ishtiyoqini oshiradi, kasb-hunarga bo`lgan qiziqishni kuchaytiradi. Zero, komillik belgisi eng avvalo ilmlilik va biron-bir hunarning mohir egasi bo`lish bilan ham belgilanadi. "Bilimdan ortiq boylik yo`q", "Bilgan o`qir, bilmagan to`qir", "Aqlning qayrogi-bilim" (1-sinf), "Bilim-baxt keltirar"(2-sinf), "Bilagi zo`r birni yiqar, bilimi zo`r mingni", "Ko`p o`qigan ko`p bilar", "Ilm olish- nina bilan quduq qazish", "Bir yigitga qirq hunar oz", "Hunar o`rganish uchun ham hunar kerak" (3-sinf), "Olim bo`lsang, olam seniki", "Hunar bo`lsa qo`lingda, non topilar yo`lingda", "Ilm-aql chirog`i"(4-sinf) kabi maqollarni o`rganish jarayonida o`quvchilarga ilm olishning afzalliklari, bilim hamisha insonni yuksaklikka eltuvchi vosita ekanligini, shuning uchun o`quvchilar hozirdanoq bilimolishga qunt bilan kirishishlari zarurligi uqtiriladi. Ilmi va bilimi orqasidan yurtimizda e`zoz topayotgan kishilar misolida bu maqollarning mazmuni ustida ishlanadi.

Ko`rinadiki, xalq maqollari boshlang`ich sinf o`quvchilarida insoniy fazilatlarni tarbiyalashda, ularda yuksak ma`naviyatni shakllantirishda, kelajakda barkamol inson bo`lib yetishishlarida juda katta rol o`ynaydi.

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